

1 **PPARA with PPARG functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 PPARA and PPARG as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors in
10 embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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